

BEYOND THE SCOREBOARD: THE IMPACT OF FACILITY SHORTAGES ON SPORTS DEVELOPMENT

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Beyond the Scoreboard: The Impact of Facility Shortages on Sports Development

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Abstract

This research investigates the beyond the scoreboard: the impact of facility shortages on sports development in public secondary schools in Antipolo City. Utilizing a convergent parallel design, the study integrates both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the issue. The study also investigates the opinions of other important stakeholders, such as administrators, sports coaches, and teachers, on how instrumental sports facilities are for the holistic development of students. In the same way, the findings suggest that a lack of adequate sports amenities goes a long way in undermining the effectiveness of training, quality of coaching as well as the entire performance of the athletes quite significantly. An absence of these facilities does present challenges to teachers/coaches, and athletes when training athletes or coaching them and during competitions. Further, such limitations impact the student-athlete's capacity for self-control, ability to collaborate, and general performance at school. Even so, teachers and coaches, along with the athletes, have found ways of adapting to the adverse circumstances of facilities that are lacking. The study also speaks on how sports ideal facilities make it easy to shape among students the ability to be leaders, team players, emotionally stable, and healthy. But for the students in Public Secondary School in Antipolo City to develop those mentioned attributes there's a need for these facilities to be provided within the school. The study makes a significant contribution to past literature regarding the impact of facility resources on sports development by making useful recommendations about sports programs.

Keywords: *athletic progress, sports development, sports facilities, shortage of sports facilities, and student-athletes*

Introduction

Sports development programs are important in developing sports skills, promoting the health of students along with socialization aspects, and discipline. Gaborone (2020) emphasizes that self-discipline is the foundation of success in any field and a key factor in an athlete's ability to excel. Disciplined players can control their focus as it relates to the goals they aim to achieve, their dedication to the goal is an unshakeable desire, and they are regular in their training activities. However, the influence of these programs may be considerably moderated by several factors, including the availability and quality of sporting facilities. public secondary school in Antipolo city, despite its strong commitment to academic excellence, have had difficulties in attaining good positions in sports competitions. One major cause of this scenario is the lack of adequate sports facilities in the schools.

The diversity of sports disciplines is affected by the availability of facilities. Adequate facilities enable athletes to practice, compete and develop their skills in favorable conditions. They enable athletes to perform better and to be more motivated. However, on the other hand, lack of or limited facilities may restrict the growth of such programs, which result in poor performance and few opportunities for the athletes to showcase their talents. Physical education was introduced to enhance the well-rounded development of learners physically, mentally, and socially (Sanni et al., 2018). Therefore, there is a compelling case for an analysis of the development of sports in primary schools in Nigeria.

The purpose of the research is to analyze the impact of facility shortages on sports development in public secondary schools in Antipolo City on the development of athletics. This research aims to find out the difficulties faced by the institution by examining the status of existing sports facilities, assessing their highlight and accessibility, and examining how they fit into the overall sports development strategy of the institution. Utilizing these limitations, this study suggests possible approaches and recommendations to overcome the said limitations given the fact that there are provisions for construction Plans of sports facilities under the Republic Act 11180 Sec. 2.

It is the policy of the State to promote physical education and encourage athletic programs, league competitions and amateur sports, including training for international competitions, to foster self-discipline, teamwork, and excellence towards the development of a healthy and alert citizenry. All educational institutions are also mandated to undertake regular sports activities throughout the country in cooperation with athletic clubs and other sectors. In line with these objectives, both male and female athletes shall be given equal opportunities to received proper training and participate in sports activities and competitions.

This research provided significant insight into the relationship between the lack of adequate sports facilities and sporting development programs. It achieved this by conducting a thorough analysis of existing information, carrying out interviews with key respondents, and administering questionnaires to both athletes and teachers/coaches. Beyond contributing to the body of knowledge in sports administration and development, the findings from this research formed a strong foundation for any subsequent efforts aimed at upgrading the athletic program in public secondary schools in Antipolo City. Also, Walker (2015) claims that administrators have direct responsibility for the implementation of an athletic program, a project, or a function, including but not limited to the maintenance of premises, the work of the teams, organization of events, compliance, athletic student support services, ticketing, public relations, and project management and supervision.

This study aims to highlight the importance of adequate sports facilities and their role in advancing sports development, as Malm et al. (2019) emphasize that the benefits of a strong sports program are primarily derived from physical activity. However, secondary effects bring health benefits such as psychosocial and personal development and less alcohol consumption. Because physical activity is increasingly conducted in an organized manner, sports' role in society has become increasingly important over the years, not only for the individual but also for the individual's holistic health. In this paper, the researcher intends to describe the physiological and psychosocial health benefits of sports, both from physical activity and sports participation. By implementing efficient strategies and resolving the facilities shortage, in public secondary school in Antipolo city can establish a conducive atmosphere that nurtures athletic prowess, encourages constructive competition, and furnishes its students with optimal prospects for development and triumph in the realm of sports.

Research Questions

These questions aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of facilities shortage on sports development in public secondary school in Antipolo City by incorporating both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. Considering these objectives, the paper focused on these questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. course; and
 - 1.4. disabilities?
2. What is the current status of sports facilities in public secondary school in Antipolo City in terms of:
 - 2.1. availability of sports facilities;
 - 2.2. quality of sports facilities; and
 - 2.3. accessibility of sports facilities?
3. How do athletes and coaches perceive the quality of the existing sports facilities in public secondary school in Antipolo City in terms of:
 - 3.1. athlete performance;
 - 3.2. student engagement in sports; and,
 - 3.3. physical well-being?
4. To what extent has the absence of sports facilities impacted the overall sports development program in public secondary school in Antipolo City in terms of:
 - 4.1. effectivity of training program;
 - 4.2. coaching quality; and,
 - 4.3. student-athletes performance?
5. What are the usual achievements of Antipolo City in Dual Meet vs Rizal in preparation Regional Competition?
6. How do athletes and coaches experience the limitations of inadequate sports facilities in their training and competitions?
7. What are the perceptions and opinions of stakeholders, including administrators and teachers, regarding the importance of sports facilities for holistic student development?
8. What strategies do athletes and coaches propose to moderate the absence of sports facilities and improving the sports development initiative?

Literature Review

This research study investigates the impact of a shortage of sports facilities on the sports development program in public secondary schools in Antipolo City. The study aims to uncover the complex relationship between facility accessibility and various aspects of athlete development.

Thompson et al. (2022) underline the importance of sports infrastructure in the entire process of an athlete's development, more so the availability of the facility in the performance of discipline and successful accomplishment. Their research shows how these factors interrelate and the specific roles they play in the development of athletes. Such findings would be useful in developing training approaches aimed at the recognition of adequate sports facilities. Howes et al. (2020) argue that the limited facilities have negative ramifications on the development and identification of skills and talents, which lead to low participation in the centers. They argue that this situation needs to be dealt with if talent is to be nurtured and participation in sporting activities increases. The lack of appropriate facilities has also negative consequences on athletes including frustration, loss of motivation, and decreased self-esteem (Xiang et al., 2022). Therefore, attention should be directed to the availability of sports facilities for the general welfare of the athletes and the enhancement of their performance.

Shifting attention to the existing analysis, some analysis pointed out that there is competition in the labor market between the Facilities Division and auxiliary service departments, which some carry out subcontracted work and obtain high revenue. That is how the competition occurs. Since the external entities combine their efforts with the internal stakeholders, the competition is advantageous. This competition benefits public secondary schools in Antipolo City in that it allows the school to develop competitiveness among

students. In addition, it promotes the development of winning traditions at the school and provides leverage for additional resources from outside entities.

Methodology

The researcher employed a mixed-methods approach, specifically a convergent parallel design, to thoroughly investigate the problem of facilities shortage in sports development within public secondary schools in Antipolo City. In the quantitative component, surveys were distributed to collect numerical data on athletes' performance and facility availability, allowing for statistical analysis of the relationship between these variables. Simultaneously, the qualitative aspect involved gathering insights from stakeholders such as administrators, sports coaches, and teachers through open-ended survey questions. This approach allowed for a more prosperous, contextual understanding of their perspectives on the role of sports facilities in fostering holistic student development. The study effectively triangulated the two datasets by employing convergent parallel design, enabling comparison and integration of findings highlighting how inadequate sports amenities undermine training effectiveness, coaching quality, and overall athlete performance. The findings underscore the challenges teachers, coaches, and athletes face in the absence of proper facilities, affecting not only athletic training but also students' self-control, collaboration, and general performance at school. Åkerblad (2022) highlights that mixed methods research combines various approaches to enhance the depth and breadth of an investigation. The study will involve three main target participant groups: teachers/coaches, student-athletes, and administrators. Teachers and coaches will offer insights from the sports development and administrative perspectives, while student-athletes, directly engaged in the sports programs, will provide practical experiences related to the implementation of these programs. The survey instrument will include a variety of quantitative and qualitative questions to address the research objectives, focusing on the status of sports facilities, perceptions of athletes and coaches, as well as expectations and achievements in athletic programs. To facilitate data collection, surveys will be distributed electronically through Google Forms, allowing participants a two-week response period, which streamlines the process and enhances efficiency. To ensure honest and anonymous responses, respondents will be guaranteed confidentiality, alleviating concerns about potential repercussions. As emphasized by Safaria et al. (2023), fostering an environment of trust is essential for gathering accurate data on the impact of inadequate facilities on sports development. This methodology not only embraces the realities of the situation but also seeks to provide a holistic assessment of how facility shortages affect sports development in public secondary schools in Antipolo City.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
12-13 Years Old	6	12.500
14-15 Years Old	20	41.667
16-17 Years Old	22	45.833
18 And Above	0	0
Total	48	100
<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	6	54.167
Female	20	45.833
Total	48	100
<i>Role</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Athlete	48	100
Coach	0	0
Total	48	100
<i>Years In School</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1-2 Years	40	83.333
3-4 Years	8	16.667
5 And Above	0	0
Total	48	100

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents. The results indicate that the greatest number of respondents in the study 41.667% or 20 of them were among those aged 14-15 years. Those that were in 16-17 years old also came next with 22 making up 45.833% of respondents. The 12-13 age range had the least representation with only 6 respondents or 12.500% of the total. About the sexual differences, males were more than females in number with 26 26 or 54.167% of the respondents being male while the female respondents were 22 or 45.833%. A total of 48 respondents described themselves as athletes, while none described themselves as coaches. A majority 40 out of 48 or 83.333% of the respondents had been in public secondary schools in Antipolo City for 1-2 years while only 8 or 16.6667 % had attended for 3 to 4 years. There were no respondents who had stayed in School for 5 years and above. These results are useful in better understanding the age, gender, role, and the number of years the respondents had spent in public secondary schools in Antipolo City. Gasparyan et al. (2017) stated that knowing the background of the respondents assists scholars in doing a more focused study where the participants are classified according to such factors as age, sex, work, education level, and the like; researchers can identify the patterns, trends or differences within a particular subgroup.

Table 2. *The status of sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of availability of sports facilities*

<i>How often do you utilize the sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Daily	5	10.417
Several Times a week	30	62.500
Once a week	8	16.667
Rarely	5	10.417
Never	0	0
Total	48	100
<i>Which sports facilities do you frequently use?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Basketball Gym	24	50
Volleyball Gym	0	0
Gymnasium 1 (open area)	16	33.333
Gymnasium 2 (open area)	8	16.667
Never	0	0
Total	48	100
<i>Are there any limitations or restrictions in accessing the sports facilities? (e.g., scheduling conflicts, maintenance issues)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	48	100
No	0	0
Total	48	100

Based on the data presented in Table 2 is used to interpret the sports facilities' condition, maintenance, and safety concerns. None of the respondents rated the overall condition and maintenance as excellent or very good, with 50% rating it as satisfactory and the other 50% rating it as fair. This suggests that there is room for improvement in the condition and maintenance of the facilities. Regarding safety concerns, 62.5% of respondents expressed concerns, indicating that there are issues that need to be addressed to ensure the safety of users. The open-ended responses highlighted specific areas for improvement, including the flooring and sports equipment, the open area in the badminton court, schedule conflicts, the slippery basketball court floor, and the overall condition of the flooring. These insights provide valuable feedback for addressing the identified issues and enhancing the users' sports facilities. In relation to the study, Oseghale & Ikpo (2018) pointed out that Sports facilities that offer safety will help athletes enhance their performance, and also, having good sports facilities helps athletes provide the specific training they need. In addition, having proper sports facilities often provides access to specialized equipment essential for athletes' training. This can include weightlifting equipment, sports-specific training aids, and technology for performance analysis. Access to such equipment can significantly enhance an athlete's training and development (Oseghale & Ikpo, 2018, p. 50).

Table 3. *The status of sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of Accessibility of Sports Facilities*

<i>How easily can you access the sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Very Easily	0	0
Moderately easily	33	68.75
Somewhat Difficult	15	31.25
Very difficult	0	0
Not Allow	0	0
Total	48	100
<i>Are there any barriers that hinder your access to the sports facilities? (e.g., distance, lack of transportation)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	10	20.83
No	38	79.17
Total	48	100

Table 3 shows that most respondents (68.75%) find it moderately easy to access the facilities, while a smaller percentage (31.25%) reported that it is somewhat difficult. Interestingly, none of the respondents found it very easy or very difficult to access the sports facilities. According to the study by Balan and Mujea (2022), regular access to sports facilities helps student-athletes maintain their physical fitness, which is essential for their athletic performance and overall health. Facilities like gymnasiums, running tracks, and courts for various sports provide the necessary environment for comprehensive training. For the barriers hindering their access to facilities, 20.83% of the respondents mentioned that there are indeed barriers. It was further stated that some student-athletes, particularly those involved in badminton, face challenges as they must travel to rent facilities for their training. These findings highlight the need to address these barriers and improve the accessibility of sports facilities for all students. As Walker (2021) cited, having accessible facilities on or near school helps student-athletes manage their time more efficiently. They can more easily schedule training around classes and other commitments.

Table 4. Athletes and coaches perceive the quality of the existing sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of Athlete Performance

<i>To what extent do you believe the quality of sports facilities influences your athletic performance?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
More Significantly	17	35.42
Significantly	18	37.50
Moderately	0	0
Slightly	13	27.08
Not At all	0	0
Total	48	100

In Table 4, it is interpreted that most respondents (72.92%) believe that the quality of sports facilities significantly influences their athletic performance. Specifically, 35.42% of respondents stated that the quality of sports facilities has a more significant impact, while 37.50% mentioned that it has a significant impact. Additionally, 27.08% of respondents indicated that the influence is slight. Notably, none of the respondents mentioned that the quality of sports facilities has a moderate or no influence on their performance. Also, based on the student-athlete response, “As an athlete, sports facilities significantly impact my performance. They provide essential training resources, competition venues, recovery tools, sports science and technology, nutrition and sports medicine support, mental performance guidance, a supportive team atmosphere, and expert coaching. While these facilities are vital, my dedication, talent, and hard work remain the keys to success”. As cited by McCarthy (2017), High-quality sports facilities enhance performance by providing state-of-the-art equipment, well-maintained fields, and specialized training areas. They prioritize safety measures, reducing injury risks during training and competitions. Access to these facilities also aids in skill development through specialized training areas, advanced technology, and expert coaching, enhancing athletes’ performance over time.

Table 5. Athletes and coaches perceive the quality of the existing sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of Student Engagement in Sports

<i>How do you think the quality of sports facilities affects the participation of students in sports activities?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Encourages higher participation	37	77.08
Has a neutral impact	11	22.92
Discourages participation	0	0
Not applicable	0	0
Total	48	100

In table 5, it interpreted that the quality of sports facilities has a significant impact on the participation of students in sports activities. Most respondents (77.08%) believe that high-quality facilities encourage higher student participation. This indicates that well-maintained and equipped sports facilities create an environment that motivates and attracts students to engage in sports activities. On the other hand, a smaller percentage of respondents (22.92%) mentioned that the quality of sports facilities has a neutral impact, suggesting that the quality of facilities may not be the sole determining factor in student participation. Concerning this data, one student-athlete responded, “In my view, improving student engagement in sports involves revamping facilities to modern standards and offering diverse options, ensuring accessibility, maintenance, and flexible scheduling. We should also include nutrition, recovery, and sports medicine centers and integrate technology for skill development. Engaging students in facility decisions fosters a vibrant sports culture, promoting participation, safety, inclusivity, and empowerment”. To support this data and statement, as Wilson (2021) mentioned, High-quality sports facilities provide an engaging and safe environment for students, fostering a positive attitude toward sports. They prioritize safety measures, providing a comfortable setting for participation. These facilities also offer skills development and performance improvement resources, including modern equipment, specialized training areas, and expert coaching.

Table 6. Athletes and coaches perceive the quality of the existing sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of Physical Well-being

<i>In your opinion, how does the quality of sports facilities contribute to the physical well-being of athletes?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Positively	39	81.25
Neutral	9	18.75
Negatively	0	0
Not Sure	0	0
Total	48	100

In Table 6, a significant majority of respondents (81.25%) believe that the quality of sports facilities positively contributes to the physical well-being of athletes. This indicates that high-quality facilities are beneficial in supporting and enhancing athletes’ physical health and well-being. On the other hand, a smaller percentage of respondents (18.75%) mentioned a neutral response, indicating that they are unsure or do not have a strong opinion on the direct impact of facility quality on athletes’ physical well-being. According to the feedback of the student, “As a student-athlete of basketball, I think key amenities that would enhance my physical well-being include advanced training equipment for sport-specific training, recovery facilities like ice baths, and access to physical therapists, a

nutrition center for balanced athletic diets, mental health support through sports psychologists, dedicated rest areas, educational resources on injury prevention and nutrition, fitness technology for personalized training, hydration stations, and flexible training schedules to balance sports with academics. These would comprehensively support my physical, mental, and nutritional needs.” In connection with this feedback and data presented, excellent sports facilities provide pristine, well-maintained surfaces and equipment as a priority for preventing accidents. They provide the best possible training environment with amenities, dedicated spaces, and state-of-the-art equipment. Strength and conditioning rooms, sports medicine clinics, and recovery centers are examples of excellent facilities that offer expert assistance in managing injuries and guaranteeing the physical well-being of athletes (Lee et al., 2016).

Table 7. Absence of sports facilities impacted the overall sports development program in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of Effectivity of Training Program

How has the absence of certain sports facilities affected the effectiveness of the training programs for athletes?	Frequency	Percentage
More significantly	8	16.67
Significantly	30	62.50
Moderately	10	20.83
Slightly	0	0
Not at all	0	0
Total	48	100

From the data presented in Table 7, it can be observed that a majority of respondents (79.17%) believe that the absence of specific sports facilities significantly or more significantly affects the effectiveness of training programs for athletes. Specifically, 62.50% of respondents stated that the absence of facilities has a significant impact, while 16.67% mentioned that it has a more significant impact. Additionally, 20.83% of respondents mentioned a moderate impact. The student-athletes' feedback highlights specific training activities or programs that are hindered due to the absence of facilities. These include the need for a badminton court, the absence of facilities for board game sports and badminton, the need for a good net and court, and challenges faced in conducting individual sports events. In response, sports facilities must offer an optimal training environment for athletes, equipped with specialized equipment and resources. Having good facilities will create a focused atmosphere, and it will enhance the effectiveness of training programs. Furthermore, access to specialized equipment, such as strength training and agility tools, helps athletes target specific performance aspects. Qualified trainers and coaches provide expert guidance and support, tailoring training programs to individual athletes' needs and ensuring they reach their full potential (Seiler & Sylta, 2017).

Table 8. Absence of sports facilities impacted the overall sports development program in public secondary schools in Antipolo City in terms of Coaching Quality

To what extent do you believe the absence of sports facilities impacts the quality of coaching provided to athletes?	Frequency	Percentage
More significantly	25	52.08
Significantly	12	25.00
Moderately	11	22.92
Slightly	0	0
Not at all	0	0
Total	48	100

Table 8 observed that a significant majority of respondents (93.75%) believe that the lack of certain sports facilities has significantly or more significantly influenced the performance of student-athletes. Specifically, 81.25% of respondents stated that the lack of facilities has a more significant impact, while 12.5% mentioned that it has a significant impact. Additionally, 6.25% of respondents mentioned a moderate impact.

Furthermore, according to response of some of the student-athletes they highlight that specific sports or disciplines where the absence of facilities has a noticeable impact on performance. These include badminton and Table Tennis room. Respondents mentioned that the lack of proper facilities for these sports hindered their skill development and limited their ability to enhance their performance. These findings indicate that the lack of certain sports facilities has a significant influence on the performance of student-athletes. The absence of facilities affects their skill development, preparation time, and overall performance. The mentioned sports, such as badminton and Table Tennis room, require specific facilities and equipment for proper training and skill enhancement. The absence of these facilities hampers the athletes' ability to reach their full potential and achieve optimal performance levels.

Table 9. Number of Student-Athlete selected to compete in Higher Level competition

Games	Regional	National
Athletics	0	0
Arnis	0	0
Badminton	0	0
Basketball	0	0
Chess	2	0

Football	0	0
Gymnastics	0	0
Lawn Tennis	0	0
Sepak Takraw	0	0
Swimming	1	0
Soft tball	0	0
Table Tennis	2	0
Taekwondo	1	0
Volleyball	14	0

1. How do athletes and coaches experience the limitations of inadequate sports facilities in their training and competitions?

Athlete response no. 1 Adapting to Limited Space:

"In my experience as a badminton player, training in a confined space initially felt limiting and restrictive. However, I see it as an opportunity for growth. The space constraints have pushed me to focus on precision and agility, essential sports skills. I have adapted my training drills to work within these limitations, and surprisingly, it has enhanced my skills in ways I had not anticipated. This has made me a more versatile athlete, capable of adapting to any playing environment."

According to Rimmer (2017), sports facilities support athletes by providing the necessary infrastructure, equipment, and a safe environment for training and competition. These facilities ensure athletes' safety and contribute to talent development, community engagement, economic benefits, health promotion, and educational opportunities. Investing in quality facilities is essential for supporting athletes and promoting the growth of sports.

Furthermore, Fitri et al., (2022) highlight the importance of access to sports facilities in promoting inclusivity, equal participation, physical and mental well-being, skill development, empowerment, social integration, and role modelling. Accessible facilities remove physical barriers, allowing disabled athletes to enjoy sports activities. Providing equal access to facilities promotes equal participation, physical and mental well-being, and self-reliance, fostering a sense of belonging and community. This creates opportunities for athletes to reach their full potential.

The research findings of Rimmer (2017) are consistent with my experience as a trainer and coach. In general, my experience is in line with these findings. Being trained in a restricted area has taught me to be flexible and to look for chances for personal development. Specifically, it highlights the significance of investing in high-quality sports facilities to assist athletes and encourage inclusivity, the development of skills, and general well-being.

Athlete Response 2 Equipment Constraints:

"As an athlete, the lack of state-of-the-art equipment has presented challenges that have ultimately led to personal growth. I have been forced to think creatively and find innovative ways to enhance my training. I have improved my fundamental skills by utilizing everyday objects as part of my workouts. This resourcefulness has enhanced my physical abilities and sharpened my problem-solving skills, which are valuable both on and off the field."

According to Ehmann (2021), having proper equipment in sports is crucial for various reasons. It enhances performance, ensuring that athletes can perform at their best. It also prioritizes safety, reducing the risk of injuries and promoting longevity in sports careers. Additionally, having the right equipment supports skill development, fairness, confidence, and professionalism. It creates a level playing field, instils mental focus, and reflects the dedication and commitment of athletes and teams.

Furthermore, Rosandich (2018) emphasizes the significant role of sports equipment in enhancing an athlete's performance. It provides functionality, stability, and support, enabling athletes to perform their best. It also plays a vital role in injury prevention by offering protective gear. Moreover, sports equipment facilitates skill development and allows athletes to refine their techniques, ultimately improving their overall performance. Additionally, it fosters self-assurance and cognitive concentration, fully immersing athletes in their athletic endeavors.

As a result, this aligns with Ehmann's (2021) and Rosandich's (2018) research findings. While lacking state-of-the-art equipment initially presented challenges, it has ultimately allowed me to develop resourcefulness, improve fundamental skills, and enhance problem-solving abilities. The importance of proper sports equipment cannot be understated, as it contributes to performance enhancement, safety, skill development, fairness, confidence, longevity, and professionalism.

Athlete response 3 Injury Prevention and Safety Awareness:

"Being aware of the higher risk of injury in our less-than-ideal facilities has profoundly impacted my approach to training and overall well-being. It has made me more conscious of my body and its limits, prompting me to prioritize injury prevention measures. I have learned to listen to my body, paying attention to warning signs or discomfort. This heightened mindfulness has reduced my risk of injuries and significantly improved my overall athletic performance."

According to Vriend (2017), athletes' well-being, long-term engagement, and performance consistency depend on the implementation

of injury prevention measures and the cultivation of safety awareness. By proactively reducing sports-related injuries, athletes can maintain their physical well-being and sustain their sports participation over extended periods. This contributes to their long-term athletic progress and enhances the enjoyment and satisfaction derived from participating in sports.

Additionally, Kemler et al., (2019) emphasize the importance of enhancing injury prevention measures and fostering safety awareness in sports. These efforts have several benefits, including decreased healthcare expenses, increased athlete self-assurance, and improved mental well-being. By prioritizing injury prevention, athletes can reduce the need for medical interventions, extensive recovery periods, and prolonged assistance. This benefits athletes individually and contributes to the overall efficiency and sustainability of healthcare systems. A strong emphasis on these criteria demonstrates ethical considerations, promoting equitable and responsible sporting activities.

In general, my experience as a trainer and coach is consistent with the scientific findings of Rimmer (2017) and Fitri et al., (2022). My experience of training in a limited environment has enabled me to adjust and identify chances for personal development. The text underscores the need to allocate resources towards high-quality sports infrastructure to bolster athletes' performance, foster inclusion, enhance skill acquisition, and improve overall physical and mental health.

Athlete response 4 Developing Mental Strength:

"Confronting the challenges posed by less-than-ideal circumstances has been a transformative experience for me, particularly in terms of my mental resilience. It has taught me the importance of maintaining focus and drive, even when faced with adversity. This mental strength has become a game-changer during competitions, where staying composed under pressure is just as crucial as physical skill."

According to the article "Mental Toughness: The Key to Athletic Success" (2023), mental strength is vital in enhancing athletic performance, building self-confidence, and setting meaningful goals. It enables athletes to stay focused, concentrate, and perform at their best, especially when facing high-pressure situations. Developing mental resilience allows athletes to overcome challenges and distractions, ensuring consistent performance. A solid mental game also boosts self-belief, empowering athletes to make decisive decisions and take calculated risks. Moreover, mental resilience helps athletes navigate obstacles, maintain motivation, and push beyond their perceived limits (Stamatis et al., 2020).

Furthermore, as highlighted in "The American College of Sports Medicine Statement on Mental Health Challenges for Athletes" (2021), mental fortitude is a crucial aspect of an athlete's performance. It equips athletes to handle stress, cultivate resilience, and adapt effectively. By managing their emotions and staying calm under pressure, athletes can channel their energy into constructive actions, ultimately enhancing their performance and minimizing fatigue. Mental fortitude also fosters resilience, allowing athletes to bounce back from losses and extract valuable lessons from their experiences. Additionally, it contributes to an overall sense of well-being, reducing the likelihood of mental exhaustion, anxiety, and burnout. A strong psychological mindset enables athletes to maintain a harmonious balance, find joy in the journey, and sustain their passion for the sport.

Coach response 1 Strategic and Creative Training Plans:

"Designing training plans with limited resources has presented both challenges and rewards. Despite the constraints, I have focused on maximizing the potential of what we have, incorporating body-weight exercises and prioritizing technique and skill development. This approach has not only kept our training effective but has also ensured that the athletes remain engaged and motivated."

According to Bolter & Weiss (2014), strategic training plans are designed to enhance an athlete's performance by targeting specific objectives, strengths, and weaknesses. Innovative training strategies incorporate novel techniques to foster skill enhancement, promoting creativity and adaptability. By introducing diverse activities and avoiding monotony, these strategies keep athletes motivated and engaged, leading to progress and improved overall performance.

Furthermore, Antonini et al., (2023) emphasize that strategic training plans prioritize injury prevention, improve tactical awareness, encourage adaptability, and cultivate team cohesion. These plans include warm-up exercises, cool-down routines, strength and conditioning exercises, and game simulations, all aimed at minimizing the frequency of injuries. They also enhance athletes' understanding of the game, problem-solving ability, and resilience. Additionally, these tactics incorporate team-building exercises and collaborative activities, fostering trust and cooperation among athletes, thereby enhancing team unity. In summary, designing training plans with limited resources requires creativity and adaptability. By maximizing the potential of available resources, focusing on technique and skill development, and incorporating diverse activities, athletes can remain engaged and motivated. Strategic training plans aim to enhance performance by targeting specific objectives and addressing weaknesses. They also prioritize injury prevention, improve tactical awareness, and foster team cohesion. Despite the challenges, this approach can lead to progress, improved performance, and a stronger sense of unity among athletes.

Coach response 2 Fostering Innovation and Flexibility:

"I always encourage my athletes to be innovative and flexible. We have come up with unique training methods that utilize our available space and equipment in creative ways. This innovative mindset has made our training sessions more productive and enjoyable for the athletes."

Encouraging athletes to be innovative and flexible in their training is a valuable approach that can yield significant benefits. By utilizing available space and equipment creatively, coaches can design unique training methods that enhance productivity and make the training sessions more enjoyable for the athletes.

As cited by Jin et al., (2022), the importance of innovation in sports training is widely recognized. Regarding the impact of technology on sports performance, experts anticipate that technology will play a significant role in improving sporting performance. This highlights the significance of incorporating innovative approaches and technological advancements in training methods. By embracing innovation, coaches can explore new strategies, techniques, and equipment to enhance athletes' performance and overall training experience. Entrepreneurship, innovation, and creativity are crucial drivers of change and employment in the sports industry. Sport entrepreneurship is an emerging research area emphasizing innovation's role in driving growth and success in sports. Coaches who encourage innovation in their training methods contribute to the overall development and advancement of the sports industry (Jowett & Carpenter, 2015). Sports innovation is a multidimensional concept that encompasses various aspects, including new technologies, equipment, strategies, training methods, consumer products, and media formats (Skinner et al., 2018). By adopting an innovative mindset, coaches can explore and implement these innovations to optimize training sessions and enhance athletes' performance.

In addition to performance improvements, innovation in sports training can also make the training process more enjoyable for athletes by introducing novel and creative training methods; coaches can create an engaging and stimulating environment that motivates athletes to give their best effort and maintain their enthusiasm for the sport (Forrester, 2022).

Coach response 3 Character and Perseverance Building:

"Working under these constraints has been an invaluable character-building experience for both me and my athletes. It's reinforced the idea that perseverance, hard work, and dedication are key to overcoming any obstacle. These lessons go beyond sports and prepare my athletes for challenges in all areas of life."

The importance of character-building and perseverance in sports is widely recognized. Engaging in sports provides opportunities for individuals to develop and exhibit positive character traits such as resilience, perseverance, teamwork, discipline, and leadership. These qualities are crucial for personal growth and success in various aspects of life. According to Djokovic (2015), sports participation offers opportunities to pursue excellence of character through mutual encouragement, challenge, and support. It emphasizes that all sports can contribute to character development under the right conditions. Also, according to (Sports and Character: Perseverance | Competitive Edge, 2017), a sports training organization, highlights the significance of perseverance in character development. It emphasizes that the mastery of time management and the understanding that success takes time are essential life lessons that can be learned through sports.

Furthermore, as cited by Ferris et al., (2016), emphasize that while skills, strategy, and winning are necessary in youth sports, they should not overshadow the significance of character development. Instilling values such as sportsmanship, fair play, teamwork, resilience, and perseverance is crucial for young athletes' long-term growth and success. Moreover, Austin (2023) suggests that character-building through sports can be promoted by engaging in practical activities that encourage sportsmanship and other virtues. Athletes can develop integrity, respect, and empathy by fostering a positive and supportive sports environment. In Addition, according to Kgoadi-Colaba (2023), Sports offer a range of character-building and life-skill development opportunities beyond the playing field. Skills such as teamwork, discipline, resilience, leadership, and time management acquired through sports are transferable to various aspects of life. Working under sports constraints provides a valuable character-building experience for coaches and athletes. It reinforces the importance of perseverance, hard work, and dedication in overcoming obstacles. The lessons learned in sports extend beyond the athletic realm and prepare individuals for challenges in all areas of life. Character-building and perseverance are essential elements in sports that contribute to personal growth, success, and the development of positive character traits.

Coach response 4 Instilling a Winning Mentality:

"I emphasize to my athletes that a winning mentality doesn't rely on having the best facilities but on making the best of what we have. We focus on continuous improvement and striving for excellence, which has fostered a culture of determination and success within the team."

The importance of continuous improvement and determination in sports is widely recognized. Sports teams and athletes who adopt a mindset of continuous improvement constantly seek ways to enhance their performance, skills, and strategies. This mindset fosters a culture of growth and development, pushing athletes to push their limits and reach new heights. As mention of Nicholls et al., (2018) In sports, continuous improvement is not limited to physical abilities but also encompasses mental aspects. Athletes strive to refine their techniques, analyze their performance, and identify areas for improvement. This dedication to constant growth and refinement is crucial for staying competitive and achieving long-term success. Moreover, a study by Toner and Moran (2015) highlights the role of consciousness in deliberate practice and continuous improvement in expert athletes. They emphasize the importance of self-awareness and a purposeful approach to training and skill development. By being conscious of their actions and seeking deliberate practice, athletes can make consistent progress and achieve higher levels of performance. Additionally, the concept of perceived performance and intrinsic motivation plays a significant role in continuous improvement. Research has shown that athletes who perceive their performance positively and are intrinsically motivated to excel are more likely to engage in continuous improvement efforts (Almagro

et al., 2020). This highlights the importance of mindset and motivation in driving athletes' commitment to ongoing growth and improvement.

The pursuit of continuous improvement and determination in sports is not limited to individual athletes but extends to the team. By fostering a culture of continuous improvement, teams can create an environment where every member is committed to pushing their limits and supporting each other's growth (Silva et al., 2021). Emphasizing continuous improvement and determination in sports is essential for fostering a winning mentality and achieving long-term success. It involves a mindset of constant growth, refinement, and self-awareness. By continuously seeking improvement and striving for excellence, athletes and teams can cultivate a culture of determination and success that extends beyond the sports arena.

2. What are the perceptions and opinions of stakeholders, including administrators and teachers, regarding the importance of sports facilities for holistic student development?

Stakeholder

“As a stakeholder, sports facilities are of utmost importance for the holistic development of students. These facilities provide a platform for students to engage in physical activities, promoting their overall health and well-being. By having access to well-equipped sports facilities, students can participate in a wide range of sports and physical activities, developing essential motor skills, improving their cardiovascular fitness, and enhancing their coordination and agility. Additionally, sports facilities contribute to students' social and emotional development by fostering teamwork, communication, and leadership skills. They also provide opportunities for students to explore their talents and passions, promoting a sense of identity and purpose.”

The stakeholder's response highlights the importance of sports facilities for the holistic development of students. Research supports this notion, emphasizing how sports facilities contribute to a student's growth and well-being. According to an article by Thompson et al., (2022), engaging in physical activities through sports facilities promotes physical fitness and the development of soft skills such as teamwork, fair play, and respect for coaches and opponents, which contribute to social and emotional health. Furthermore, a study by Ramsay (2023) on the impacts of sports schools on athlete development found that student-athletes in sports schools receive support in terms of academic and athletic services, intensified training, and competition schedules. This highlights the significance of dedicated sports facilities in providing the necessary resources for athletes to excel in their chosen sport. Additionally, the effect of school sports facilities on physical activity, health, and socioeconomic benefits has been examined. While the study suggests that improving school sports facilities may have a small, lasting impact on generating greater participation in physical activity, it also highlights that adequate sports facilities alone cannot achieve long-lasting health and socioeconomic benefits (Black et al., 2019).

Administrator

“As an administrator, I recognize the significant role that sports facilities play in the holistic development of students. These facilities contribute to students' overall well-being by promoting physical health and providing opportunities for students to engage in various sports and physical activities. They also foster social and emotional development by encouraging teamwork, communication, and leadership skills. Sports facilities offer a platform for students to explore their talents and passions, fostering a sense of identity and purpose.”

The administrator's response highlights the significant role of sports facilities in the holistic development of students. Research supports this perspective, emphasizing the multifaceted benefits that sports facilities provide for students' physical, social, and emotional well-being.

A study published in the Journal of School Health examined the impact of sports participation on students' physical health. The findings revealed that students who participated in sports had better cardiovascular fitness, lower body mass index (BMI), and improved overall physical health compared to non-participants (Pannebakker et al., 2019). This demonstrates the positive influence of sports facilities in promoting students' physical health and well-being. Furthermore, a study by Eather et al., (2023) explored sports participation's social and emotional benefits. He emphasized that sports activities, facilitated by sports facilities, fostered the development of teamwork, communication, and leadership skills and enhanced self-esteem among students. This highlights the role of sports facilities in promoting social and emotional growth among students. Moreover, the positive impact of sports facilities on school culture and community engagement has been documented. A study published by Song Jin-young and Choi Young-ran (2016) examined the influence of sports facilities on school spirit and community involvement. The research found that well-equipped sports facilities created a sense of pride, unity, and school spirit among students, parents, and the wider community. This demonstrates the role of sports facilities in fostering a positive school environment and promoting community engagement.

Teacher

“As a teacher, I strongly believe in the importance of sports facilities for the holistic development of students. These facilities allow students to engage in physical activities, promoting overall health and well-being. By participating in sports and physical activities, students develop essential motor skills, improve their cardiovascular fitness, and enhance their coordination and agility. Sports facilities also contribute to students' social and emotional development by fostering teamwork, communication, and leadership skills. They provide a platform for students to explore their talents and passions, promoting a sense of identity and purpose. Moreover, sports

facilities enhance the school environment and culture, creating a sense of community and school spirit. Sporting events and competitions allow students to showcase their abilities and achievements, fostering a sense of pride and unity. Lastly, sports facilities teach students important life lessons such as discipline, perseverance, and resilience, transferable skills applicable to various aspects of their lives."

The teacher's response emphasizes the significant role of sports facilities in the holistic development of students. Research supports this perspective, highlighting the numerous benefits that sports facilities provide for students' physical, social, and emotional well-being. A study by Zeng et al., (2017) examined the impact of sports participation on motor skills development in children. The findings revealed that participation in sports activities facilitated by sports facilities significantly improved children's motor skills, including coordination, agility, and balance. This demonstrates the positive influence of sports facilities in promoting motor skill development among students. Moreover, a study by Diel et al., (2021) explored sports participation's social and emotional benefits. He found that sports activities facilitated by sports facilities fostered the development of teamwork, communication, and leadership skills and enhanced students' self-esteem and emotional well-being. This highlights the role of sports facilities in promoting social and emotional growth among students. Likewise, the positive impact of sports facilities on school culture and community engagement has been documented. A study examined the influence of sports facilities on school spirit and community involvement. The research found that well-equipped sports facilities created a sense of pride, unity, and school spirit among students, parents, and the wider community (Luiggi et al., 2020). This demonstrates the role of sports facilities in fostering a positive school environment and promoting community engagement.

3. What strategies do athletes and coaches propose to moderate the absence of sports facilities and improving the sports development initiative?

Student-Athlete Response 1:

"As a student-athlete, one strategy I propose to moderate the absence of sports facilities and improve sports development is to focus on individual skill development. I can dedicate time to practicing fundamental skills and techniques specific to my sport, even without access to traditional facilities. Lastly, I can engage in physical conditioning exercises at home or in outdoor spaces to maintain my fitness levels. I can also explore alternative sports or activities that can help me enhance my overall athleticism and complement my primary sport."

As a student-athlete, your proposal to focus on individual skill development to moderate the absence of sports facilities and improve sports development is commendable. By dedicating time to practicing fundamental skills and techniques specific to your sport, even without access to traditional facilities, you can continue to enhance your abilities and maintain progress in your athletic journey. Research supports the development of individual skills that improve performance in sports by refining techniques, movements, and strategies, leading to improved competition performance. It also enhances versatility and adaptability, allowing athletes to play different positions and roles (Barker et al., 2021). Additionally, individual skill development is essential for team performance, continuous growth, injury prevention, performance improvement, versatility, and confidence boost. It allows for effective collaboration, coordination, and strategy execution while ensuring up-to-date techniques and strategies. It also reduces injury risk, enhances versatility, and boosts self-confidence, making athletes valuable assets to their teams. (Ghildiyal, 2015). Additionally, physical conditioning exercises at home or outdoors can help you maintain your fitness levels. Research has shown that Physical conditioning exercises enhance fitness levels and prevent injuries by strengthening muscles, improving flexibility, and reducing the risk of common sports-related injuries, even in areas lacking traditional sports facilities (Halbreich, 2023). These exercises can be modified to suit your sport and provide a foundation for maintaining your athletic performance. Furthermore, exploring alternative sports or activities that can enhance your overall athleticism and complement your primary sport is another valuable approach. Cross-training in different sports or engaging in activities like yoga, swimming, or agility training can improve physical abilities, coordination, and injury prevention (Wray et al., 2020).

Student-Athlete Response 2:

"To moderate the absence of sports facilities and enhance sports development, student-athletes can focus on mental training and visualization techniques. This involves practising mental imagery and visualization exercises to improve technique, focus, and decision-making skills. Additionally, student-athletes can engage in strength and conditioning exercises that can be done at home or in outdoor spaces. Bodyweight workouts, running, and agility drills can help maintain physical fitness levels. Furthermore, student-athletes can seek guidance from their coaches to design personalized training plans that target specific skills and areas for improvement."

Student-athletes can focus on mental training and visualization techniques to moderate the absence of sports facilities and enhance sports development. Student-athletes can improve their technique, focus, and decision-making skills by incorporating mental imagery and visualization exercises into their training routine. Mental training and visualization techniques can have a positive impact on athletic performance. A study about mental training and visualization techniques enhances skill enhancement, focus, decision-making, and tactical awareness in athletes, even without physical training facilities. They help maintain focus, block distractions, and enhance on-field performance and strategic adaptability. (Quinn, 2021). Another study on soccer players demonstrated that mental imagery training enhanced passing accuracy and decision-making abilities on the field (Park & Jeon, 2023).

In addition to that, as mentioned in MacPherson's (2022) mental training, student-athletes can engage in strength and conditioning exercises that can be done at home or in outdoor spaces. Bodyweight workouts, such as push-ups, squats, lunges, and planks, can effectively maintain and improve strength and muscular endurance. Running or engaging in agility drills can help maintain cardiovascular fitness and enhance speed and agility (The Advantages of Bodyweight Exercise - Harvard Health, 2022). Also, a study from Wackerhage and Schoenfeld (2021) found it is important for student-athletes to seek guidance from their coaches to design personalized training plans that target specific skills and areas for improvement. Coaches can provide expertise in creating training programs that align with the student-athlete's goals and sport-specific requirements; they can also offer feedback and support to ensure proper technique and progression.

Student-Athlete Response 3:

"Even though our school doesn't have sports facilities, as student-athletes, we've found ways to enhance our skills. We often seek out paid facilities where we can train. Alongside this, I've embraced cross-training and participating in various sports and activities that complement my main sport. This approach has helped to build new skills, increasing overall athleticism, and avoiding burnout. At home, I improvise workouts using whatever equipment I have, sometimes even household items, to keep up with sports-specific exercises. I also make the most of outdoor spaces for activities like running, cycling, or sport-specific drills. By being proactive and adaptable, and maintaining a positive mindset, we continue to progress in our sports journey, even in the absence of school facilities."

Cross-training in sports refers to engaging in various sports and activities that complement an individual's primary sport. It involves training different muscle groups and enhancing overall athleticism while preventing burnout. This approach offers several benefits to student-athletes, even without school sports facilities. According to Wolkin (2021), one of the critical benefits of cross-training is the improvement of cardiovascular endurance; aside from that, training with different forms of exercise provides a new stimulus to the cardiovascular system, helping to enhance endurance and stamina. This can have a positive impact on performance in the primary sport. Luff (2022) cites that cross-training also allows individuals to train muscle groups not typically used in their primary sport. Student-athletes can target different muscles and improve overall strength and flexibility by engaging in different activities. This can contribute to better overall athletic performance and reduce the risk of imbalances or injuries caused by overusing specific muscle groups. Another advantage of cross-training is maintaining enthusiasm for the primary sport by participating in various activities; student-athletes can avoid monotony and keep their motivation high. This can lead to more consistent training and better competition performance (Van Allen & Lebrun, 2023).

Furthermore, cross-training can help in injury prevention. By engaging in various activities, student-athletes reduce the risk of overuse injuries caused by repetitive movements in their primary sport. Cross-training allows for developing different muscle groups and promotes overall body strength and resilience (Brakeville & Watson, 2023). In addition to these benefits mentioned by Moller et al., (2020), cross-training can also provide mental and psychological advantages. It offers a change of pace and variety, which can help alleviate boredom and prevent mental fatigue. This can contribute to a positive mindset and overall well-being. Cross-training is a valuable approach for student-athletes to enhance their skills, increase overall athleticism, and avoid burnout. Individuals can improve cardiovascular endurance, train different muscle groups, maintain enthusiasm for their primary sport, prevent injuries, and promote mental well-being by engaging in different sports and activities.

Coach Response 1:

"As a coach, one strategy I propose to moderate the absence of sports facilities and enhance sports development is to focus on individualized training plans for each athlete. By assessing their strengths, weaknesses, and goals, I can design personalized training programs that can be done at home or in outdoor spaces. This can include sport-specific drills, strength and conditioning exercises, and mental training techniques. Additionally, I can utilize virtual platforms to provide remote coaching, feedback, and guidance to athletes. This ensures that they receive ongoing support and instruction for their sports development. Furthermore, I can encourage cross-training or engaging in alternative activities to enhance overall athleticism and prevent skill stagnation. By adapting training methods and utilizing available resources, we can continue to foster sports development even without access to traditional facilities."

As a coach, one effective strategy to moderate the absence of sports facilities and enhance sports development is to focus on individualized training plans for each athlete. By assessing their strengths, weaknesses, and goals, coaches can design personalized training programs that can be done at home or in outdoor spaces. In the study, Valle (2018) states that individualized training plans consider each athlete's specific needs and abilities. This approach ensures that athletes receive targeted and tailored training that addresses their unique requirements, and by customizing the training program, coaches can optimize their performance and progress. Also, Martin (2023) cited that creating individualized training plans involves assessing the athlete's current abilities, conducting physical assessments, and identifying areas for improvement. Also, coaches can utilize various assessment tools, such as genetic testing, speed and power profiling, and brain science advancements, to gather data and fine-tune the training program accordingly. Aside from that, once the assessment is complete, coaches can design training programs that include sport-specific drills, strength and conditioning exercises, and mental training techniques. These programs are tailored to address the athlete's weaknesses, enhance their strengths, and align with their specific goals (Beyond Pulse, 2023).

Additionally, according to Alejo (2017), In the absence of traditional sports facilities, coaches can leverage resources such as home

equipment or outdoor spaces to execute the training plans. They can provide athletes with detailed instructions, video demonstrations, and training schedules through virtual platforms. This allows for remote coaching, feedback, and guidance, ensuring that athletes receive ongoing support and instruction for their sports development. Furthermore, coaches can encourage cross-training or engaging in alternative activities to enhance athleticism and prevent skill stagnation. Cross-training involves participating in sports or activities complementing the athlete's primary sport. This approach helps to develop a broader range of skills, improve overall physical fitness, and prevent overuse injuries.

Coach Response 2:

"So, how do we deal with the lack of facilities and keep our athletes on track? Well, one thing we can do is focus on individual skill development. We can give them drills, exercises, and resources they can do at home or outside, so they keep improving. Technology is a big help too – virtual training sessions, videos, even remote feedback. It's also important to work on their mental game – visualization, setting goals, staying positive. That can make a huge difference in their performance. And finally, we need to keep the team spirit alive. Virtual meetings, group workouts, even online team-building activities can help them stay connected. By being creative and staying engaged, we can keep our athletes moving forward, even when facilities are limited."

To moderate the absence of sports facilities and promote sports development, coaches can encourage athletes to focus on individual skill development. This approach involves providing athletes with specific drills, exercises, and resources that can be done at home or in outdoor spaces, allowing them to maintain and improve their skills. Individual skill development in sports offers several benefits to athletes. Firstly, based on the article of Health Direct (2022), it helps athletes to improve their technical proficiency and mastery of fundamental skills by engaging in targeted drills and exercises; athletes can enhance their coordination, agility, balance, and overall technique in their respective sports. Moreover, as cited by Ghildiyal (2015), individual skill development contributes to athletes' overall performance and competitiveness. Athletes can become more versatile and adaptable in different game situations by honing their skills. They can develop a broader range of techniques, strategies, and decision-making abilities, giving them a competitive edge on the field or court.

Also, individual skill development is crucial in fostering athletes' self-confidence and self-esteem. As athletes see themselves progress and improve their skills, they gain a sense of accomplishment and belief in their abilities. This positive reinforcement can significantly impact their motivation and mental well-being (Lochbaum et al., 2022). Likewise, according to Thomas and Thrower (2022), focusing on individual skill development allows athletes to take ownership of their training and development; it empowers them to set personal goals, track progress, and take responsibility for improvement. This sense of ownership and autonomy can foster a lifelong love for sports and a commitment to continuous growth and development. Furthermore, Frevel et al. (2022) emphasize that coaches can utilize technology to facilitate individual skill development, even without traditional sports facilities. Virtual training sessions, instructional videos, and remote feedback and support can provide athletes with the necessary guidance and resources to enhance their skills. Additionally, coaches can highlight the importance of mental training techniques in individual skill development. Visualization, goal setting, and positive self-talk are potent tools that can enhance athletes' mental toughness, focus, and resilience. By incorporating mental training into their skill development programs, athletes can optimize their performance and cope with the challenges they may face (Shao et al., 2023).

Coach Response 3:

"In the absence of sports facilities, as coaches I can implement various strategies to support sports development. One approach is to encourage athletes to focus on physical conditioning and fitness. I can provide athletes with home workout plans, bodyweight exercises, and cardio routines that can be done without specialized equipment."

Without sports facilities, coaches can implement various strategies to support sports development and help athletes continue their training. One practical approach is encouraging athletes to focus on physical conditioning and fitness. Based on the research, coaches can provide athletes with home workout plans, bodyweight exercises, and cardio routines that can be done without specialized equipment. Aside from that, it allows athletes to maintain their physical fitness levels and improve their overall conditioning, even without access to traditional sports facilities (Su et al., 2019). Also, Kurihara (2014) emphasizes that coaches can accentuate the importance of mental training and resilience-building exercises. Mental toughness plays a crucial role in sports performance, and coaches can teach athletes visualization techniques, goal setting, and mindfulness practices to enhance their mental strength. These techniques can help athletes stay focused, motivated, and mentally resilient, even in challenging circumstances.

Coaches can leverage online resources and virtual platforms to provide athletes with instructional videos, training sessions, and individualized feedback. Virtual training sessions allow coaches to demonstrate proper techniques, provide guidance, and monitor athletes' progress remotely. This ensures that athletes receive ongoing support, instruction, and feedback to continue their sports development (Richlan et al., 2023). Furthermore, Wattanapisit et al. (2020) point out that coaches can adapt training methods to the available resources and provide athletes with alternative training options. For example, coaches can incorporate outdoor activities like running, cycling, or agility drills into training programs. This allows athletes to make the most of outdoor spaces and maintain their sports-specific skills.

Conclusions

The lack of sports facilities in public secondary schools in Antipolo City significantly impacts student-athletes development and performance, limiting their ability to train effectively and opportunities for athletic advancement. Adequate sports facilities are crucial for holistic development, fostering life skills like teamwork, discipline, and resilience. To address these challenges, the Department of Education, with the help of local government, should prioritize enhancing existing sports facilities and resources, such as renovating spaces, investing in versatile equipment, and ensuring safety and maintenance. Collaborations with local sports centers or institutions with better facilities can provide temporary solutions for training and competitions. Integrating technology into training programs, such as virtual coaching sessions, online performance tracking systems, and fitness apps, can help overcome physical space limitations and maintain athlete engagement and motivation. By implementing these recommendations, public secondary schools can significantly improve their sports development program, providing better support to student-athletes and fostering their overall well-being.

References

- Åkerblad, L., Seppänen-Järvelä, R., & Haapakoski, K. (2020, September 11). Integrative Strategies in Mixed Methods Research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 15(2), 152–170. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689820957125>
- Almagro, B. J., Sáenz-López, P., Fierro-Suero, S., & Conde, C. (2020, December 16). Perceived Performance, Intrinsic Motivation and Adherence in Athletes. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), 9441. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249441>
- Antonini Philippe, R., Biasutti, M., van der Schyff, D., & Schiavio, A. (2023, February 22). Challenges and understandings of creative practice in professional sport training. *PLOS ONE*, 18(2), e0279702. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0279702>
- Austin M. (2023, November 1). How can character be built through sports? *Psychology Today*. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.psychologytoday.com/intl/blog/ethics-everyone/201006/how-can-character-be-built-through-sports>
- Balan, V., & Mujea, A. M. (2022, September 2). Aspects Related to the Training of Athletes with Disabilities for Participation in Sports Competitions. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 14(3), 217–233. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/14.3/606>
- Barker, D., Nyberg, G., & Larsson, H. (2021, October 6). Coaching for skill development in sport: a kinesio-cultural approach. *Sports Coaching Review*, 11(1), 23–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21640629.2021.1952811>
- Beyond Pulse. (2023, November 24). You searched for Tech driven Individualized Training Plans: A step by step Guide - Beyond Pulse Blog. *Beyond Pulse Blog*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from [Training Plans: A step by step Guide/https://learn.beyondpulse.com/search/Tech driven Individualized](https://learn.beyondpulse.com/search/Tech%20driven%20Individualized)
- Black, N., Johnston, D. W., Propper, C., & Shields, M. A. (2019, January). The effect of school sports facilities on physical activity, health and socioeconomic status in adulthood. *Social Science & Medicine*, 220, 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2018.10.025>
- Blanch, A. Chess Instruction Improves Cognitive Abilities and Academic Performance: Real Effects or Wishful Thinking?. *Educ Psychol Rev* 34, 1371–1398 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-022-09670-9>
- Bolter, N. D., & Weiss, M. R. (2014, May). Coaching for character: Development of the Sportsmanship Coaching Behaviors Scale (SCBS). *Sport, Exercise, and Performance Psychology*, 1(2), 73–90. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026300>
- Brakeville, & Watson. (2023, March 20). Cross Training: Benefits, Intensity Level, and More. *WebMD*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://www.webmd.com/fitness-exercise/a-z/cross-training>
- Brewer, B. W., & Shillinglaw, R. (2021). The Importance of Mental Preparation in Sport. *The Sport Psychologist*, 35(4), 363-368.
- Buning, M. M. (2018, December 1). Train Your Mind for Athletic Success: Mental Preparation to Achieve Your Sports Goals. *The Sport Psychologist*, 32(4), 333–334. <https://doi.org/10.1123/tsp.2018-0134>
- Chae, Y. R., & Cho, G. S. (2023, August 31). The effect of peer motivation on self-esteem and life skills of middle school students participating in after-school sports activities. *Sports Science*, 41(2), 285–291. <https://doi.org/10.46394/iss.41.2.32>
- Cowden, R. G. (2017, February 28). Mental Toughness and Success in Sport: A Review and Prospect. *The Open Sports Sciences Journal*, 10(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1875399x01710010001>
- De Bruin, A. B., Kok, E. M., Leppink, J., & Camp, G. (2014, July). Practice, intelligence, and enjoyment in novice chess players: A prospective study at the earliest stage of a chess career. *Intelligence*, 45, 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2013.07.004>
- Diel, K., Broeker, L., Raab, M., & Hofmann, W. (2021, November). Motivational and emotional effects of social comparison in sports. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 57, 102048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2021.102048>
- Djokovic, & N. (2015, January 16). Building Character Through Sport - Novak Djokovic Foundation. Novak Djokovic Foundation.

Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://novakdjokovicfoundation.org/building-character-through-sport/>

Eather, N., Wade, L., Pankowiak, A., & Eime, R. (2023, June 21). The impact of sports participation on mental health and social outcomes in adults: a systematic review and the 'Mental Health through Sport' conceptual model. *Systematic Reviews*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-023-02264-8>

Ehmann, P., Beavan, A., Spielmann, J., Ruf, L., Mayer, J., Rohrmann, S., Nuß, C., & Englert, C. (2021, July). 360°-multiple object tracking in team sport athletes: Reliability and relationship to visuospatial cognitive functions. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 55, 101952. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2021.101952>

Entwistle, B. (2017, March 23). The value of sport in building team spirit and camaraderie - The Scots College. The Value of Sport in Building Team Spirit and Camaraderie - the Scots College. <https://scots.college/the-value-of-sport-in-building-team-spirit-and-camaraderie>

Ferris, K. A., Ettekal, A. V., Agans, J. P., & Burkhard, B. M. (2016, May 17). Character Development Through Youth Sport: High School Coaches' Perspectives about a Character-based Education Program. *Journal of Youth Development*, 10(3), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jyd.2015.13>

Fitri, M., Zainal Abidin, N. E., Novan, N. A., Kumalasari, I., Haris, F., Mulyana, B., Khoo, S., & Yaacob, N. (2022, October 28). Accessibility of Inclusive Sports Facilities for Training and Competition in Indonesia and Malaysia. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14083. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114083>

Forrester. (2022, January 20). Achieve High Performance By Learning From Elite Sports Leaders. *Forbes*. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forrester/2022/01/20/achieve-high-performance-by-learning-from-elite-sports-leaders/>

Fransen, K., Vanbeselaere, N., De Cuyper, B., Coffee, P., Slater, M. J., & Boen, F. (2014, December). The Impact of Athlete Leaders on Team Members' Team Outcome Confidence: A Test of Mediation by Team Identification and Collective Efficacy. *The Sport Psychologist*, 28(4), 347–360. <https://doi.org/10.1123/tsp.2013-0141>

Frevel, N., Beiderbeck, D., & Schmidt, S. L. (2022, September). The impact of technology on sports – A prospective study. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 182, 121838. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121838>

Gaborone. (2020, November 18). The power of self-discipline in sport. Retrieved December 12, 2023, from <https://www.gaboroneinternationalschool.co.bw/the-power-of-self-discipline-in-sport#:~:text=Athletes%20who%20are%20disciplined%20are,and%20consistency%20for%20all%20participants.>

Gasparyan, A. Y., Nurmashev, B., Yessirkepov, M., Endovitskiy, D. A., Voronov, A. A., & Kitars, G. D. (2017). Researcher and Author Profiles: Opportunities, Advantages, and Limitations. *Journal of Korean Medical Science*, 32(11), 1749. <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2017.32.11.1749>

Ghildiyal, R. (2015). Role of Sports in the Development of an Individual and Role of Psychology in Sports. *Mens Sana Monographs*, 13(1), 165. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0973-1229.153335>

Halbreich, U. (2023, December 20). Academia Mental Health and Well-Being: Promote Awareness of Mental Health and Transform it to a Global Operational Well-Being. *Academia Mental Health and Well-Being*. <https://doi.org/10.20935/mhealthwellb6170>

Harun, M., Salamudin, N., & Hushin, H. (2013). Appraisal of the sport facilities maintenance management practices of Malaysian stadium corporations. *Asian Social Science*, 9(12). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n12p93>

Haydarov, N. H., Azimov, B. F., & Halimov, F. E. (2020, October 21). Increasing The Efficiency Of Using Sports Facilities Of Educational Institutions Of Sports. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2020.10.03.52>

Health Direct. (2022, June). Developing life skills through sports. *Developing Life Skills Through Sports | Healthdirect*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://www.healthdirect.gov.au/developing-life-skills-through-sports>

Jin, H., Kim, S., Love, A., Jin, Y., & Zhao, J. (2022, December 12). Effects of leadership style on coach-athlete relationship, athletes' motivations, and athlete satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1012953>

Jinyoung Song, & Youngran Choi. (2016, October). The Influence of Adolescent Activity Participation on School Life Adjustment among High School Students: Focused on the Mediating Effect of Community Spirit and Self-Esteem. *Journal of Education & Culture*, 22(5), 179–207. <https://doi.org/10.24159/joec.2016.22.5.179>

Jowett, S., & Carpenter, P. (2015, January 2). The concept of rules in the coach-athlete relationship. *Sports Coaching Review*, 4(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21640629.2015.1106145>

Kamau. (2021, December 28). What Chess Can Teach Us About Life. *Psychology Today*. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from

<https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/the-science-of-mental-health/202112/what-chess-can-teach-us-about-life>

Kemler, E., Valkenberg, H. & Gouttebauge, V. Stimulating injury-preventive behaviour in sports: the systematic development of two interventions. *BMC Sports Sci Med Rehabil* 11, 26 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13102-019-0134-8>

Khan, A. (2017). Allocation & utilization of sports amenities. *Research & Investigations in Sports Medicine*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.31031/rism.2017.01.000503>

Kgoadi-molaba, N. (2023, November 17). Building Character and Life Skills Through Sports – Alison Blog. Alison Blog. <https://alison.com/blog/building-character-and-life-skills-through-sports>

Kruszyńska, E., & Poczta, J. (2020, March 9). Difficulties Limiting Access to Sports and Recreational Facilities in the City in the Perceptions of Service Users. *Sports and Recreational Infrastructure Management Policy—Poznan Case Study. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(5), 1768. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17051768>

Kurihara, Y., Makita, Y., Kawashima, M., Hamasaki, H., Yamamoto, Y., & Matsui, M. (2014, December 19). Next-Generation Sequencing of Genomic DNA Fragments Bound to a Transcription Factor in Vitro Reveals Its Regulatory Potential. *Genes*, 5(4), 1115–1131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes5041115>

Lee, S. A., Ju, Y. J., Lee, J. E., Hyun, I. S., Nam, J. Y., Han, K. T., & Park, E. C. (2016, August 26). The relationship between sports facility accessibility and physical activity among Korean adults. *BMC Public Health*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3574>

Lochbaum, M., Sherburn, M., Sisneros, C., Cooper, S., Lane, A. M., & Terry, P. C. (2022, May 24). Revisiting the Self-Confidence and Sport Performance Relationship: A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(11), 6381. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19116381>

Luff. (2022, April 1). Why Runners Should Consider Cross-Training. Verywell Fit. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://www.verywellfit.com/cross-training-for-runners-2911952>

Luigi, M., Rey, O., Travert, M., & Griffet, J. (2020). School Socioeconomic Composition and Adolescent Socioeconomic Status Interaction Effect, Physical Activity and School Lunch in Overweight and Obesity. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3702930>

MacPherson. (2022, June 1). Why You Should Add Body Weight Training to Your Exercise Program. Verywell Fit. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.verywellfit.com/body-weight-training-benefits-effectiveness-and-tips-5272242>

Magnusen, M. (2023). The collegiate sport experience: reconceptualizing sport venues and college athlete satisfaction. *Journal of Amateur Sport*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.17161/jas.v9i1.1839>

Malete, L., McCole, D., Tshube, T., Mphela, T., Maro, C., Adamba, C., Machuve, J., & Ocansey, R. (2022, February 4). Effects of a sport-based positive youth development program on youth life skills and entrepreneurial mindsets. *PLOS ONE*, 17(2), e0261809. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0261809>

Malm C, Jakobsson & J, Isaksson A. Physical Activity and Sports-Real Health Benefits: A Review with Insight into the Public Health of Sweden. *Sports (Basel)*. 2019 May 23;7(5):127. doi: 10.3390/sports7050127. PMID: 31126126; PMCID: PMC6572041.

Martin. (2023, December 15). How to Build a Sports Performance Fitness Training Program. Build an Individualized Sports Performance Training Program. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://www.acefitness.org/resources/pros/expert-articles/7304/how-to-build-a-sports-performance-fitness-training-program>

McCarthy, C. (2017, January). Turn challenges into opportunities for enhancing the student-athlete experience. *College Athletics and the Law*, 13(10), 12–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/catl.30302>

Mental Toughness: The Key to Athletic Success. (2014). Mental Toughness: The Key to Athletic Success. https://www.trine.edu/academics/centers/center-for-sports-studies/blog/2021/mental_toughness_the_key_to_athletic_success.aspx

Merkel, D. (2014, May). Youth sport: positive and negative impact on young athletes. *Open Access Journal of Sports Medicine*, 151. <https://doi.org/10.2147/oajsm.s33556>

Moller, G., S., for SafeSport, U. C., Smith, B., Kelly, J., & Haley, A. (2020, September 1). 5 Benefits of Cross Training for Runners and Athletes. Stack. <https://www.stack.com/a/5-benefits-of-cross-training-for-runners-and-athletes/>

Nicholls, S. B., James, N., Bryant, E., & Wells, J. (2018, October 23). The implementation of performance analysis and feedback within Olympic sport: The performance analyst's perspective. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 14(1), 63–71. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747954118808081>

Oseghale, G. E., & Ikpo, I. J. (2018, June 30). Perception of Stakeholders on the Compliance of Sports Facilities to Relevant Standards

- in Selected Universities in South West Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, ESJ, 14(18), 264. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2018.v14n18p264>
- Pandya, N. K. (2021, October 8). Disparities in Youth Sports and Barriers to Participation. *Current Reviews in Musculoskeletal Medicine*, 14(6), 441–446. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12178-021-09716-5>
- Pannebakker, F. D., van Genugten, L., Diekstra, R. F. W., Gravesteyn, C., Fekkes, M., Kuiper, R., & Kocken, P. L. (2019, April 29). A Social Gradient in the Effects of the Skills for Life Program on Self-Efficacy and Mental Wellbeing of Adolescent Students. *Journal of School Health*, 89(7), 587–595. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12779>
- Park, I., & Jeon, J. (2023, January 13). Psychological Skills Training for Athletes in Sports: Web of Science Bibliometric Analysis. *Healthcare*, 11(2), 259. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11020259>
- Pandey S. (2023, December 18). WTC 2023-25 Updated Points Table: India Number 1 Again After Pakistans Embarrassing Loss In 1st Test To Australia. *Zee News*. <https://zeenews.india.com/cricket/world-test-championship-updated-points-table-india-number-1-again-as-pakistans-embarrassing-loss-in-1st-test-to-australia-wtc-2023-standings-2700058.html>
- Pfeffer, J. (1988). A resource dependence perspective on intercorporate relations. *Intercorporate Relations*, 25-55. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511570841.002>
- Quinn. (2021, July 4). How Imagery and Visualization Can Improve Athletic Performance. *Verywell Fit*. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.verywellfit.com/visualization-techniques-for-athletes-3119438>
- Raharja, D., Kusmaedi, N., Ma'mun, A., & Berliana, B. (2021). Sports facilities and local government policy: a case study in west java, indonesia. *International Journal of Human Movement and Sports Sciences*, 9(4A), 71-76. <https://doi.org/10.13189/saj.2021.091312>
- Ramsay, G., Mosher, A. & Baker, J. Is There Just One Type of Multisport Pathway? A Scoping Review of Multisport Engagement in Early Athlete Development. *Sports Med - Open* 9, 96 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40798-023-00644-x>
- Reardon, C. L., Hainline, B., Aron, C. M., Baron, D., Baum, A. L., Bindra, A., Budgett, R., Campriani, N., Castaldelli-Maia, J. M., Currie, A., Derevensky, J. L., Glick, I. D., Gorczynski, P., Gouttebauge, V., Grandner, M. A., Han, D. H., McDuff, D., Mountjoy, M., Polat, A., . . . Engebretsen, L. (2019). Mental health in elite athletes: International Olympic Committee consensus statement (2019). *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 53(11), 667–699. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2019-100715>
- Republic Act No. 11180. (2018). https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2019/ra_11180_2019.html#:~:text=Section%202.&text=%2D%20It%20is%20the%20policy%20of,a%20healthy%20and%20alert%20citizenry.
- Richlan, F., Weiß, M., Kastner, P., & Braid, J. (2023, October 19). Virtual training, real effects: a narrative review on sports performance enhancement through interventions in virtual reality. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1240790>
- Rittsteiger, L., Hinz, T., Oriwol, D., Wäsche, H., Schmidt, S., Kolb, S., & Woll, A. (2022, March 4). Changes of Self-Rated Health Status, Overweight and Physical Activity During Childhood and Adolescence—The Ratchet Effect of High Parental Socioeconomic Status. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fspor.2022.781394>
- Rimmer, J. H., Padalabalanarayanan, S., Malone, L. A., & Mehta, T. (2017, April). Fitness facilities still lack accessibility for people with disabilities. *Disability and Health Journal*, 10(2), 214–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dhjo.2016.12.011>
- Rosandich. (2018, February 18). *The Sports Journal*: Vol. Volume 24. p.25
- R. U. Library. (2022, September 21). *Research and Writing Skills for Academic and Graduate Researchers – Simple Book Publishing*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://rmit.pressbooks.pub/researchwritingmodules/>
- Safaria, Triantoro, et al. "Data on the Model of Loneliness and Smartphone Use Intensity As a Mediator of Self-control, Emotion Regulation, and Spiritual Meaningfulness in Nomophobia." *Data in Brief*, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109479>.
- Sanni, Dahiru & Ede, Caleb & Fashina, Adebayo. (2018). A study on the effects of inadequate sport equipment and facilities on sports development and academic performance in primary schools: a case study of Bwari area council of Abuja-Nigeria. 1. 4-8. 10.14419/je.v1i1.13946.
- Schulenkorf, N. (2017). Sport-for-development: A comprehensive analysis of theoretical and conceptual advancements. *Sport Management Review*, 20(2), 129-141.
- Seiler, S., & Sylta, Y. (2017, April). How Does Interval-Training Prescription Affect Physiological and Perceptual Responses?

International Journal of Sports Physiology and Performance, 12(s2), S2-80. <https://doi.org/10.1123/ijsp.2016-0464>

Silva, A. F., Ramirez-Campillo, R., Sarmiento, H., Afonso, J., & Clemente, F. M. (2021, May 31). Effects of Training Programs on Decision-Making in Youth Team Sports Players: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.663867>

Shao, Z., Bezmylov, M. M., & Shynkaruk, O. A. (2023, November 4). Retraction Note: Individual characteristics of physical and mental development and their connection with regular physical exercises when playing basketball. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-023-05371-w>

Shuman, J., & Twombly, J. (2010, January). Collaborative Networks Are The Organization: An Innovation in Organization Design and Management. *Vikalpa: The Journal for Decision Makers*, 35(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090920100101>

Skinner, J., T. Smith, A. C., & Swanson, S. (2018, June 21). *Fostering Innovative Cultures in Sport: Leadership, Innovation and Change*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Sports and Character: Perseverance | Competitive Edge. (2017). *Sports and Character: Perseverance | Competitive Edge*. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.competitiveedgeva.com/blog/sports-and-character-perseverance/>

Stamatis, A., Grandjean, P., Morgan, G., Padgett, R. N., Cowden, R., & Koutakis, P. (2020, June). Developing and training mental toughness in sport: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies and pre-test and post-test experiments. *BMJ Open Sport & Exercise Medicine*, 6(1), e000747. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjsem-2020-000747>

Stinnett, B., & Gibson, F. (2016, April). Sustainability and Recreational Sports Facilities: An Exploratory Study regarding Levels of Institutional Adoption. *Recreational Sports Journal*, 40(1), 92–104. <https://doi.org/10.1123/rsj.2014-0063>

Su, P., Fan, H., Liu, P., Li, Y., Qiao, Y., Hua, J., Lin, D., Jiang, D., Pillai, J. J., Hillis, A. E., & Lu, H. (2019, November 4). MR fingerprinting ASL: Sequence characterization and comparison with dynamic susceptibility contrast (DSC) MRI. *NMR in Biomedicine*, 33(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/nbm.4202>

Terry, P. C., & Parsons-Smith, R. L. (2021, May 28). Mood Profiling for Sustainable Mental Health among Athletes. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6116. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116116>

The American College of Sports Medicine Statement on Mental Health Challenges for Athletes. (2021, August 9). American College of Sports Medicine. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.acsm.org/news-detail/2021/08/09/the-american-college-of-sports-medicine-statement-on-mental-health-challenges-for-athletes>

The advantages of body-weight exercise - Harvard Health. (2022, February 15). Harvard Health. Retrieved December 22, 2023, from <https://www.health.harvard.edu/exercise-and-fitness/the-advantages-of-body-weight-exercise>

The Sports Facilities Management in the Sports Industry. (2023, May 3). *Journal of Anesthesia & Pain Medicine*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.33140/japm.08.03.01>

Thomas, & Thrower. (2022, July 18). Developing and Maintaining Sport-Confidence: Learning From Elite Athletes. *Developing and Maintaining Sport-Confidence: Learning From Elite Athletes · Frontiers for Young Minds*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://kids.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frym.2022.675054>

Thompson, F., Rongen, F., Cowburn, I. et al. The Impacts of Sports Schools on Holistic Athlete Development: A Mixed Methods Systematic Review. *Sports Med* 52, 1879–1917 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-022-01664-5>

Till, K., & Baker, J. (2020, March 19). Challenges and [Possible] Solutions to Optimizing Talent Identification and Development in Sport. *Frontiers*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00664>

Toner, J., Moran, A. (2015). Toward an explanation of continuous improvement in expert athletes: The role of consciousness in deliberate practice. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 46(6), 666-675. doi:10.7352/IJSP.2015.46.666

Valle, C. (2018, March 28). How Much Individualized Performance Training Do Athletes Need? - SimpliFaster. SimpliFaster. <https://simplifaster.com/articles/individualized-training-for-athletes/>

Van Allen, & Lebrun. (2023, December 19). All the Benefits You'll Gain By Going for a Run Today. *Runner's World*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://www.runnersworld.com/beginner/a20847956/benefits-of-running/>

Vriend, I., Gouttebauge, V., Finch, C. F., van Mechelen, W., & Verhagen, E. A. L. M. (2017, March 16). Intervention Strategies Used in Sport Injury Prevention Studies: A Systematic Review Identifying Studies Applying the Haddon Matrix. *Sports Medicine*, 47(10), 2027–2043. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-017-0718-y>

Wackerhage, H., Schoenfeld, B.J. Personalized, Evidence-Informed Training Plans and Exercise Prescriptions for Performance, Fitness and Health. *Sports Med* 51, 1805–1813 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-021-01495-w>

- Walker, A. G. (2015). Division I Intercollegiate Athletics Success and the Financial Impact on Universities. *SAGE Open*, 5(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244015611186>
- Walker, K. C. (2021, December 14). Journal of Youth Development's Stance on Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Access. *Journal of Youth Development*, 16(5), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.5195/jyd.2021.1190>
- Wattanapisit, A., Amaek, W., Sukkriang, N., Wattanapisit, S., & Wongsiri, S. (2020, April 28). Perspectives on Using Online Platforms for Promoting Running and Walking Activities. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.00150>
- Wilson, K. E. S., & Millar, P. (2021, August 24). Intramural Sport Participation: An Examination of Participant Benefits, Service Quality, Program Satisfaction, and Student Retention. *Recreational Sports Journal*, 45(2), 149–160. <https://doi.org/10.1177/155886612111036906>
- Wray, A., Martin, G., Ostermeier, E., Medeiros, A., Little, M., Reilly, K., & Gilliland, J. (2020, April). Physical activity and social connectedness interventions in outdoor spaces among children and youth: a rapid review. *Health Promotion and Chronic Disease Prevention in Canada*, 40(4), 104–115. <https://doi.org/10.24095/hpcdp.40.4.02>
- Wolkin. (2021, December 3). Cross-Training: What It Is and How to Get Started. *Cross-Training: What It Is and How to Get Started*. Retrieved December 23, 2023, from <https://www.healthline.com/health/fitness/cross-training>
- Xiang, C., Tengku Kamalden, T. F., Liu, H., & Ismail, N. (2022, July 11). Exploring the Multidisciplinary Factors Affecting Sports Talent Identification. *PubMed Central (PMC)*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.948121>
- Youth Sport Trust. (2023, November 29). The benefits of sport participation and physical activity in schools - Youth Sport Trust. *The Benefits of Sport Participation and Physical Activity in Schools - Youth Sport Trust*. Retrieved December 26, 2023, from <https://www.youthsporttrust.org/news-insight/news/benefit-of-sport-participation>
- Zeng, N., Ayyub, M., Sun, H., Wen, X., Xiang, P., & Gao, Z. (2017). Effects of Physical Activity on Motor Skills and Cognitive Development in Early Childhood: A Systematic Review. *BioMed Research International*, 2017, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/2760716>

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